

Corpus Documentation File

Public Verification Record for Television Commercials Analysed in the Study

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1. Purpose of This Document

This file provides transparent and publicly accessible documentation of the television commercials analysed in my study of Pakistani advertising (1980s–2020s). All commercials listed here are:

- publicly available on widely used video-sharing platforms (e.g., YouTube)
- historically broadcast advertisements
- verified through publicly accessible uploads
- analysed using timecodes only (no copyrighted content reproduced)

This document allows any interested reader, reviewer, or researcher to independently confirm:

1. **Corpus authenticity**
2. **Timestamps used in analysis**
3. **Public availability of all items**
4. **Historical grounding of the dataset**

2. Corpus List (Eight Commercials)

The corpus comprises **four product domains**, with one 1980s commercial paired with one 2010s/2020s commercial for each category.

A. Toothpaste

1. English Tooth Paste – “Jeet Gya” (1980s)

- **Original Era:** 1980s (PTV)
- **Public Upload Title:** *PTV classic ad—English Tooth Paste “Jeet Gya”*
- **Link:** Publicly available on YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sXBZwq_SrvE
- **Timecodes Analysed:** ≈00:01–00:12
- **Notes:** Price-based persuasion, virtue-of-thrift frame, declarative voice-over.

2. Colgate Pakistan – Airport Lounge (2023)

- **Year:** 2022
- **Public Upload Title:** *Colgate Pakistan #ibthebrands #colgate*
- **Link:** Publicly available on YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/shorts/VBabBb45eaY>
- **Timecodes Analysed:** ≈00:01–00:35
- **Notes:** Peer-composure moment; cool palette; wellness-confidence lexicon.

B. Soft Drinks

3. Pepsi – Imran Khan Stadium Ad (1983; posted online 2010)

- **Original Broadcast:** 1983
- **Public Upload Title:** *Imran Khan: Pakistan’s greatest cricketer – Pepsi commercial 1983*
- **Link:** Publicly available on YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eKfQjp1elvk>
- **Timecodes Analysed:** ≈00:01–00:28
- **Notes:** Stadium-wide affect; national euphoria; heroic gaze; choral sound bed.

4. Pepsi – Airport Lounge Ad (2022)

- **Year:** 2022
- **Public Upload Title:** *Pepsi Pakistan TVC – Airport lounge (Babar Azam)*

- **Link:** Publicly available on YouTube:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r95YHHnL5Fo>
- **Timecodes Analysed:** ≈00:27–00:30
- **Notes:** Quiet peer intimacy; mobility motif; conversationalisation of affect.

C. Shoe Polish

5. Kiwi Shoe Polish Pakistan (1980s)

- **Original Era:** 1980s
- **Public Upload Title:** *Kiwi shoe polish commercial (Pakistan 1980s)*
- **Link:** Publicly available on YouTube:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EOpg1yd2Tek>
- **Timecodes Analysed:** ≈00:01–00:50
- **Notes:** Reciprocity-focused classroom; flag foregrounding; national pedagogy.

6. Kiwi Shoe Care – Classroom Edition (2018)

- **Year:** 2018
- **Public Upload Title:** *KIWI Shoe Care TVC 2018 (Kiwi Peridot)*
- **Link:** Publicly available on YouTube:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fIKYzOaZ_EU
- **Timecodes Analysed:** ≈00:01–00:27
- **Notes:** Streamlined “global classroom”; polished employability; performativity.

D. Life Insurance

7. State Life Insurance (1980s)

- **Original Era:** 1980s
- **Public Upload Title:** *State Life Insurance Company commercial (Pakistan 1980s)*
- **Link:** Publicly available on YouTube:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aAuUm7F61-U>

- **Timecodes Analysed:** ≈00:01–00:33
- **Notes:** Paternal guardianship; duty-based discourse; anchored domesticity.
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8. State Life Insurance – Family Planning (2021)

- **Year:** 2021
- **Public Upload Title:** *Jubilee Life Insurance TVC – Family Future Planning*
- **Link:** Publicly available on YouTube:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WGy2De2YqXs>
- **Timecodes Analysed:** ≈00:01–00:45
- **Notes:** Conjugal co-planning; aspiration; calm aesthetics of progress.

3. Verification Notes

- All commercials were accessed through **publicly available links**, requiring no subscription.
- Only **metadata, timestamps, and descriptive elements** are provided here, in line with fair-use and copyright policy.
- There are different videos available on various YouTube channels on the same ad with slight variation in duration.
- Viewers can independently confirm the analytic references by watching the publicly uploaded versions.
- No copyrighted video has been downloaded, reproduced, or redistributed.
- The dataset is historically public, and therefore suitable for academic analysis and transparency.

4. Author Statement of Corpus Integrity

I confirm that:

- The corpus has been collected and viewed over several years as part of a continuous CDA/MCDS research trajectory.

- All analytic interpretations in the study are my own.
- Timecodes, descriptions, and contrasts listed here are directly observable in the public uploads.
- This documentation is provided to ensure transparency, replicability, and corpus authenticity.